

SECTION OF HISTORICAL SCIENCES

SYSTEM OF UPBRINGING AND EDUCATION IN TRADITIONAL KAZAKH SOCIETY

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Abstract

Currently, the main components of the education and upbringing system in traditional Kazakh society are of great interest. Each of these components played an important role in the formation of Kazakh culture and way of life. Traditional upbringing and Muslim education created a rich and multi-layered system of values. This article examines the forms of traditional regulation of life: social and national traditions and customs, rules and norms of behavior that form moral ideals, special attention is paid to the basics of charity. These traditions and values continue to influence modern Kazakh society, and they are an important part of Kazakhstan's cultural heritage.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, system of upbringing and education, religious traditions, charity.

An essential element of the spiritual heritage of the historical past of Kazakhstan is religious tolerance and multi-confessionals. For centuries, various religious communities have coexisted on the territory of Kazakhstan, including Islam, Orthodoxy, Catholicism, Protestantism, Buddhism, Judaism and others. Freedom of religion and respect for different religions and cults were rooted in Kazakh society. The culture of the Kazakh people includes values such as hospitality, respect for elders, etc. Nauryz Meiram, Kurban Ait, Ramadan, Easter and Christmas are significant holidays that celebrate communication between different ethnic groups and religious communities. This promotes rapprochement and mutual understanding between different cultures and peoples, and also preserves the religious and ethnic diversity of Kazakhstan.

Kazakh culture and educational traditions have many unique features that reflect the richness of their ethnic heritage. In the system of education and upbringing of traditional Kazakh society, several main components can be distinguished, including:

1. Traditional education;
2. Education among the ruling elite;
3. Muslim education.

Education in traditional Kazakh society was carried out through the transfer of values and norms of behavior from the older generation to the younger. Parents, older relatives and society as a whole played an important role in shaping moral principles and ethics. Education includes teaching young people traditional customs and rules of behavior in society. This was important for maintaining sociocultural integrity and stability. Honor (namys) and dignity play an important role in Kazakh culture. "According to folk wisdom, a young man should be "segiz kyrly, bir syrly" and have versatile skills and abilities. In particular, a certain moral and psychological standard of personality was developed, the essence of which was the well-known aphorism, which is literally translated as follows: "A real horseman has eight facets of quality and is able to keep a secret," i.e. a person must have the following skills and abilities: love for his native land, hard work,

perseverance in trouble, courage in battle, knowledge of the genealogy of his family, poetic talent, resourcefulness and wit, and master horse riding techniques. These requirements for education stemmed from the multi-structured lifestyle of the Kazakhs." [1].

In the Middle Ages and during the heyday of the Kazakh khanates, education was available mainly to the elite - rulers, nobility and representatives of the upper class of society. This education included training in complex management skills and exposure to the culture of neighboring countries. The Kazakh elite not only valued traditional education, but also acquired knowledge in various fields, including languages and diplomatic skills. S. B. Bronevsky states: "they send their sons and close relatives to St. Petersburg and Beijing at the same time" [2]. Ak suyek (white bone) is the highest class in Kazakh society, which included the *tore* and *khans*. Members of this group had special privileges and rights, including the right to occupy the khan's throne. Belonging to this class at birth gave a special status and the opportunity to participate in political power. I. P. Falk notes: "According to the information of some tsarist officials of that time, among the Kazakh Chingizids there were many Muslim-educated persons who were educated in Muslim mektebs and madrassas of Khiva and Bukhara." [3, c. 120]. S. B. Bronevsky in his notes "On the Kyrgyz-Kaisaks of the Middle Horde" notes: "Among the Soltans there are very sensible people, they are distinguished from the common people by their good looks, their slender figure, they know the Tatar literacy, the nobility of the origin of the Soltans is visible at first glance." [2]. I. G. Georgiy also notes some elements of democratic behavior in the public life of the Kazakh elite: "Their noble and rich people live exactly the same as commoners. They treat people like brothers; and since they are still free people, then everyone, as soon as they get rich, becomes just as noble." [4].

P. Pallas, in his description of the state and classes of the Kazakh people, also emphasizes that a distinctive feature of the Kazakh worldview is the concepts of liberty, freedom, independence: "The numerous Kyrgyz

people live in unlimited freedom in comparison with the Kalmyks, who have so many small rulers over them. Every Kyrgyz person lives like a free master, and therefore the Kyrgyz people are not as terrible as other enemies. However, each generation or aimak has a leader over it, to whom all those descended from the same tribe render voluntary obedience. Those who have a larger number of subordinates in their department are called khans and sultans. There are also other ranks under their jurisdiction, namely: nobles, called bis; respectable people of the old generation, Khoja, and others, called Murzas" [5].

The third most important component of the education and upbringing system of Kazakh society was Muslim education. With the introduction of Islam in the 9th century, madrassas began to be created, which offered training in the Koran, Sunnah (collections of hadiths of the Prophet Muhammad) and spiritual sciences.

The history of Muslim education and mosques in Kazakhstan reflects the rich heritage and important role of Islam in shaping the culture and way of life of this country. Mentions of mosques, construction began in the 9th century in Taraz, indicate the deep roots of Islam in Kazakhstan. "Thanks to Arabic-language written sources, it became known that in 893 a mosque was built in the city of Taraz. Currently, historians conditionally consider it one of the first mosques in the republic. Meanwhile, archaeologists who carried out excavations in Otrar and nearby settlements report the found remains of a mosque with a dome, which was mentioned by the historian al-Maqdisi (10th century) in one of his works." [6]. Мечети были центрами религиозного образования и местами для молитв и spiritual practice. During the Middle Ages, mosques performed not only religious functions, but also served as centers of education and culture. They promoted the spread of knowledge and allowed people to study Islam and other spiritual aspects. It is important to note that religious life flourished in Kazakhstan before the Mongol invasion. This demonstrates the deep religious tradition in this region.

Within the framework of this study, special attention should be paid to the basics of the formation of charitable activities. Charity in the Muslim community has deep roots in the religious teachings of Islam. In Islam, charity is seen as an act of mercy, one of the values that is required of every Muslim. Islam places great importance on mercy and caring for others. The hadith says that after the death of a person, his deeds and efforts cease, but only three things remain: alms, useful knowledge and a good child who remembers him in his prayers. This highlights the importance of mercy and caring for others in Islam [7].

Muslims believe that all good deeds and donations have religious and spiritual significance. Zakat, which means giving and supporting the poor and needy, is one of the five pillars of Islam and is mandatory for Muslim believers. Islam also encourages giving and serving the community, especially in times of distress and need. This allows Muslims to show concern for others and support those who are in difficult situations.

Infaq, or donation, is considered the most perfect form of charity in Islam. It involves donating your time, financial resources and effort to help others. Muslims believe that donating property and resources for good

causes brings them spiritual blessings and strengthens their connection with Allah [8].

Thus, charity and donation are an integral part of Islamic belief and practice. Muslims strive to embody the principles of their religion in their daily lives.

Muslim upbringing and education played an important role in the formation of the religious and cultural identity of the Kazakh people. Charity can be considered as one of the forms of pro-social behavior, since it is a specific manifestation of voluntary help and care for others. Pro-social behavior may include not only charitable donations, but also other forms of helping, such as providing personal support, friendly communication, or physical assistance. Parenting is the process of shaping the character, values, skills and knowledge of children so that they can become responsible, emotionally mature and productive members of society. Parenting included education, development of social and moral skills, and support and care for physical and emotional well-being. Charity, in turn, helps create a favorable environment for raising children. It included various forms of assistance to children and their families, such as financial support, infrastructure development and much more.

Thus, one of the key goals of education in Kazakh culture is the formation of moral qualities, such as respect for history, a sense of belonging to one's homeland and cultural roots, and showing mercy, caring and helping one's neighbor. These traditional values and approaches to education have deep roots in the history and culture of Kazakhstan and continue to be important in modern society. These values contribute to the strengthening and preservation of Kazakh identity.

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